
EXPLORING CONTEXT-SPARSE GLITCH TOKENS IN LLMs: INVESTIGATING ADVERSARIAL VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Glitch tokens are anomalous subword units that consistently trigger unexpected, unstable, or unsafe behaviors in large language models (LLMs). Some popular examples of such tokens include “SolidGoldMagikarp”, “PsyNetMessage”, and “petertodd”. Prior work has largely attributed the vulnerability to data sparsity - tokens that occur too infrequently in pretraining data, leading to poorly trained embeddings. However, this framing overlooks the concept of context sparsity. We hypothesize that a distinct class of glitch tokens emerges not due to rarity, but because they occur in narrow or repetitive contextual environments. These tokens can lead to jailbreaking and adversarial attacks on LLMs. We systematically investigate context-sparse glitch tokens across multiple families of open-source models (Gemma, LLaMA, and Mistral). Using semantic clustering, diversity scoring, and sequential n-gram analysis, we characterize tokens with limited contextual variety and evaluate their impact on robustness. Our experiments reveal mixed evidence for context sparsity effects on the HarmBench dataset, when injected at suffix positions in prompts or embedded within chat templates. These findings broaden the understanding of glitch vulnerabilities, showing that they are not simply artifacts of token rarity but reflect both contextual patterns and structural weaknesses in how LLMs process conversations.

Keywords Glitch Tokens · Large Language Models · Adversarial Attacks · Context Sparsity · LLM Security

1 Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) tokenize natural language into subword units using algorithms such as byte-pair encoding (BPE) [Sennrich et al., 2015] or SentencePiece [Kudo and Richardson, 2018], which map text into discrete tokens. These tokenizers sometimes create unusual artifacts - tokens that are rare or poorly represented in the training distribution. Prior work has shown that such glitch tokens can cause unsafe and nonsensical completions, or even bypasses of safety filters.

These studies documented artifacts such as:

- Tokens with unusually high embedding norms
- Subwords with unstable leading/trailing space variants
- Rare character sequences (e.g., corrupted Unicode fragments)

The standard explanation is *data sparsity*. Some tokens occur too rarely for models to learn robust embeddings, leaving them undertrained. However, frequency alone does not fully explain the phenomenon. Many frequently occurring tokens still act as glitches, not because they lack exposure, but because they only appear in rigid, repetitive, or highly localized contexts.

This is termed *context sparsity*. For example, a token might almost always follow the same word sequence, occur only in formulaic text (legal boilerplate, URLs, markup), or appear disproportionately in non-natural contexts. The model may fail to generalize it across diverse linguistic contexts. Such tokens "overfit" to rigid local patterns, making them fragile when recontextualized in adversarial settings.

While adversarial vulnerabilities have been extensively studied in vision models [Szegedy et al., 2013, Goodfellow et al., 2014], their manifestation in language models through tokenization artifacts represents a distinct challenge. Unlike pixel-space perturbations in computer vision, token-level vulnerabilities emerge from the discrete nature of language representation and the complex interaction between tokenization, embedding quality, and contextual usage patterns.

This work explores context-sparse glitch tokens and evaluates their correlation with adversarial vulnerability, to test whether injecting such tokens into different structural positions (user prompt suffix vs. chat template suffix) produces safety failures.

2 Related Work

Glitch token research has emerged as an important aspect of LLM vulnerabilities, with early work establishing fundamental detection methodologies and attack vectors. Land and Bartolo [2024] first systematically identified tokens with anomalous embedding norms, demonstrating that rare or undertrained subwords like “SolidGoldMagikarp” and “petertodd” could destabilize model generation and produce nonsensical outputs. Their frequency-based analysis established the dominant paradigm that data sparsity - tokens appearing fewer than 100 times in training - directly correlates with instability. This foundational work introduced key detection methods, including high embedding norm identification, unstable space-variant analysis, and rare character sequence flagging.

Building on these detection capabilities, subsequent research expanded into gradient-based optimization approaches. Wu et al. [2024] moved beyond simple frequency analysis to examine token gradient behavior during inference, using discrete optimization to systematically mine tokens that consistently trigger unsafe completions across model vocabularies. Complementing this, Zhang et al. [2024] developed ensemble-based detection methods combining embedding anomalies, gradient instabilities, and output coherence metrics, while proposing targeted fine-tuning as a mitigation strategy rather than vocabulary filtering.

Parallel to detection efforts, adversarial applications research has demonstrated the practical security implications of glitch phenomena. Geiping et al. [2024] expanded the threat landscape by systematically categorizing attacks beyond simple jailbreaking. The work demonstrated extraction attacks that leak hidden system prompts, denial-of-service attacks that force models to generate thousands of tokens through repetitive patterns, and misdirection attacks that manipulate user trust through fake URLs and refund approvals. Critically, these attacks exploited specific glitch tokens like “Mediabestanden” and tokenizer artifacts from code-heavy training data, revealing that even heavily RLHF-aligned models [Ouyang et al., 2022] could be compromised with remarkable efficiency, achieving near-perfect attack success rates using just 8–256 strategically chosen tokens.

Lin et al. [2025] demonstrated that the vulnerability extends to seemingly trivial modifications - appending a single space character towards the end of the model’s chat template could break safety alignment, achieving 100% attack success rates on architectures like Vicuna-7B and Guanaco-7B. This minimal perturbation attack reveals a fundamental weakness in how models process tokenization boundaries: single spaces in training data typically precede lists or enumerated instructions, causing models to shift into instruction-following mode and override safety refusal training.

While this work has significantly advanced our understanding of glitch vulnerabilities, it predominantly emphasizes frequency-based mechanisms like undertrained embeddings, rare tokens, or anomalous character sequences with rarity as the primary explanatory factor. Our work extends this literature by introducing context sparsity as a distinct vulnerability dimension: the hypothesis that even frequent tokens can exhibit adversarial behavior when their training contexts are overly rigid, repetitive, or semantically narrow. This reframes the problem from “instability driven solely by rarity” to “fragility induced by narrow contextual distributions”, thereby broadening the taxonomy of glitch vulnerabilities beyond simple frequency thresholds.

3 Methodology

3.1 Experimental Setup

We evaluated three open-source language models representing different architectural families and parameter scales: Gemma-3-1B-it [Team et al., 2024], LLaMA-2-7B-Chat [Touvron et al., 2023], and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 [Jiang et al., 2023]. These models were selected for their widespread adoption, public availability, and documented safety alignment procedures, making them suitable testbeds for adversarial evaluation.

3.2 Glitch Token Selection

Our approach to identifying context-sparse glitch tokens combines three complementary methods: semantic clustering, diversity scoring, and sequential n-gram analysis. Each method targets different aspects of contextual rigidity.

3.2.1 Semantic Clustering

To capture the semantic diversity of token contexts, we extracted 5-token context windows from a combined corpus of OpenWebText [Gokaslan and Davis, 2019] and C4 [Raffel et al., 2020], sampling 10,000 documents to ensure computational tractability while maintaining representativeness. For each target token, we collected all surrounding contexts and embedded them using Sentence-BERT [Reimers and Gurevych, 2019] (all-MiniLM-L6-v2), a model trained to produce semantically meaningful sentence embeddings. These context embeddings were then clustered using DBSCAN [Ester et al., 1996] with parameters $\epsilon = 0.15$ and minimum samples of 2, allowing the algorithm to identify natural semantic groupings without requiring a predetermined number of clusters. Tokens whose contexts formed few distinct clusters relative to their frequency were flagged as potentially context-sparse.

3.2.2 Diversity Scoring

Building on the clustering analysis, we developed a composite diversity score to quantify contextual variety. For tokens occurring at least 50 times in our corpus, we sampled up to 100 contexts per token to ensure statistical reliability. Each context window consisted of 15 tokens surrounding the target token, with the target itself masked to focus on contextual patterns rather than self-similarity.

The diversity metric combines three complementary measures. First, average cosine similarity captures the overall semantic coherence of contexts, with high values indicating rigid contextual patterns. Second, the standard deviation of pairwise similarities measures variability in how contexts relate to each other. Third, cluster diversity quantifies the ratio of distinct semantic clusters to total contexts, reflecting whether contexts span multiple semantic domains or concentrate in narrow usage patterns.

These components are weighted to emphasize different aspects of contextual diversity. Tokens were categorized as low-diversity (context-sparse), medium-diversity, or high-diversity based on threshold values derived from the distribution of scores across the vocabulary. Additionally, we categorized tokens by type (function words, numbers, punctuation, word fragments) to enable systematic comparison across linguistic categories.

3.2.3 Sequential N-gram Analysis

To complement semantic methods, we analyzed sequential predictability by examining ordered n-gram patterns following each token. Using a sliding window approach, we extracted sequences of 1–3 tokens immediately after each target token and computed the empirical probability that specific sequences consistently follow particular tokens. For tokens occurring at least 20 times, we flagged those where any following sequence appears with probability exceeding 75%, indicating rigid sequential constraints. Tokens were further categorized using Unicode character classes (alphabetical, numerical, punctuation, symbols, whitespace) to understand which types of sequences create predictable patterns. The 150 tokens with highest sequential predictability were selected for adversarial evaluation.

3.3 Injection Strategy

To evaluate the adversarial potential of context-sparse tokens, we employed two injection strategies targeting different structural positions in model inputs. First, we appended tokens to the suffix position of user prompts, a common attack vector in adversarial research. Second, following Lin et al. [2025], we injected tokens directly into chat templates at the boundary between user input and model response, specifically after the closing instruction marker but before generation begins. This second approach tests whether structural placement within conversation infrastructure amplifies adversarial effectiveness compared to surface-level prompt modifications.

3.4 Evaluation Protocol

We constructed a standardized evaluation pipeline using HarmBench [Mazeika et al., 2024], utilizing the 320-prompt test set that serves as the standardized benchmark for evaluating the safety of large language models (LLMs) against harmful content generation.

For each model and injection strategy, we generated completions for both baseline prompts and glitch-injected variants. Inference was performed using batched generation on Vertex AI with A100 GPUs, maintaining consistent temperature

and sampling parameters across all experiments. Generated outputs were classified as harmful or safe using the HarmBench classifier, an automated evaluator trained to detect policy violations. We computed attack success rate (ASR) as the proportion of prompts yielding harmful completions, calculated on a per-token, per-model basis to enable direct comparison between baseline and injection conditions. This metric quantifies the degree to which specific tokens compromise model safety when inserted at strategic positions. The code used for this study is available [here](#).

4 Experiments

4.1 Baseline Replication

We first replicated existing glitch detection pipelines to identify candidate tokens for adversarial evaluation. GlitchMiner identified anomalous embeddings with high norms and isolated clusters, while Magikarp reproduced instability from leading-space vs. non-leading-space tokens.

This process yielded several categories of potentially problematic tokens: partial words and subwords, control characters (e.g., `\x7f`, `\t`, `\x17`), code-related snippets (`=`, `'`, `[`, `oreAndOnline`), and garbled encoding artifacts (`ÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃÃ`) along with non-English characters.

Results Testing these tokens on smaller models (Neo-125M, GPT-2, DistilGPT) confirmed their disruptive effects and validated our pipeline correctness. When evaluating injection positions, we found that suffix placement consistently outperformed prefix and middle positions across all models, with suffix injection fundamentally altering the distribution of predicted next tokens compared to clean prompts.

4.2 Diversity Score Based Analysis

We analyzed tokens that occur at least 50 times, sampling up to 100 contexts per token. For each occurrence, we extract a context window of 15 tokens around the target token, excluding the target itself (which is replaced with `[MASK]`). These contexts are embedded using the SentenceTransformer (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) model, and semantic groupings are identified with DBSCAN clustering ($\epsilon = 0.15$, `min_samples=2`).

To quantify contextual diversity, we compute a sparsity score that combines three complementary measures:

$$\text{Sparsity Score} = 0.4 \times (1 - \text{avg_similarity}) + 0.3 \times \text{similarity_std} + 0.3 \times \text{cluster_diversity} \quad (1)$$

where `avg_similarity` captures how semantically similar the contexts are (inverted so higher values indicate more diversity), `similarity_std` measures the variation in pairwise similarities between contexts, and `cluster_diversity` represents the ratio of distinct semantic clusters to total contexts.

The formula weights average similarity most heavily (0.4) as the primary indicator of contextual rigidity, since tokens appearing in highly similar contexts suggest narrow usage patterns. Similarity standard deviation (0.3) captures variability in how contexts relate to each other, while cluster diversity (0.3) measures whether contexts form distinct semantic groups. This combination targets tokens that consistently appear in repetitive linguistic environments.

Lower sparsity scores indicate tokens that appear in narrow, repetitive contextual environments. Tokens are flagged as context-sparse if their cluster diversity falls below 0.15, average similarity exceeds 0.85, or overall sparsity score drops below 0.3.

Tokens are also categorized into types such as function words, numbers, punctuation, and word fragments to enable systematic comparison of ASR outcomes across low, medium, and high-diversity groups as well as across token types.

To evaluate the adversarial potential of these context-sparse tokens, we selected approximately 150 tokens spanning low, medium, and high diversity buckets. For each token, we ran the complete HarmBench prompt set with suffix token insertion and measured attack success rates on a per-token, per-model basis across Gemma, Mistral, and LLaMA.

Results Contrary to our hypothesis, correlation analysis revealed no significant relationship between diversity scores and attack success rates. As shown in Figure 1, while we expected decreasing diversity scores to correlate with increasing ASR, the data showed no clear pattern. Tokens with low diversity scores did not consistently produce higher ASRs than high-diversity tokens, indicating that context sparsity as measured by our diversity metric does not reliably predict adversarial vulnerability.

Figure 1: Correlation between diversity scores and attack success rates (ASR) across three model families. Each panel shows the relationship for Gemma-3-1B-it (left), Mistral-7B (center), and LLaMA-2-7B (right). The scatter plots reveal no significant correlation ($r \approx 0$), with substantial variance across all diversity score ranges, indicating that context sparsity as measured by our diversity metric does not reliably predict adversarial vulnerability.

4.3 N-gram Based Analysis

We identified tokens with high sequential predictability by analyzing ordered n-gram patterns that follow each token. Using a sliding window approach, we extracted sequences of 1–3 tokens immediately following each target token and calculated the probability that specific sequences consistently appear after particular tokens. For tokens occurring at least 20 times, we flagged those where a following sequence appears with probability $\geq 75\%$, indicating rigid sequential constraints. We categorized the tokens using Unicode character categories (alphabetical, numerical, punctuation, symbols, whitespace, other) to understand the types of sequences that create predictable patterns. The top 150 tokens with the highest sequential predictability were selected for adversarial evaluation.

Results Baseline ASRs were 8.4375% (Gemma), 17.5% (Mistral), and 2.8125% (LLaMA), consistent with official HarmBench benchmarks. The highest observed ASRs were 14.37% (Gemma), 25.3125% (Mistral), and 5.3125% (LLaMA), achieved by the token "variety" for Gemma and Mistral, and partial word "ustom" for LLaMA. These tokens were selected for their extremely high sequential predictability (i.e., preceding probability ≈ 1.0) identified during the N-gram analysis, confirming they are instances of context-sparse tokens. However, these increases were modest and inconsistent across models. Correlation analysis between preceding probability and attack success rates revealed no significant relationship (Figure 2), contradicting the hypothesis that tokens with higher sequential predictability would exhibit greater adversarial vulnerability. The data showed substantial scatter with correlation coefficients near zero across all three model families, indicating that rigid sequential patterns do not reliably predict glitch token behavior.

Further analysis of token characteristics across ASR quartiles showed that tokens in the first quartile (highest ASRs) were predominantly subwords and short words, but this pattern lacked statistical significance across all model families ($p > 0.05$, chi-square test). Figure 3 displays the distribution of token categories across ASR buckets for Mistral, revealing considerable variability within each category and no clear systematic relationship between token type and adversarial effectiveness.

4.4 Chat Template Modification

Chat models process inputs through a hidden chat template that encodes roles such as system messages, user turns, and assistant responses to structure model interactions. Rather than limiting our analysis to user-visible prompts, we extended glitch token insertion into these internal templates, following the approach of Lin et al. [2025]. Tokens were appended immediately after the [/INST] marker but before the model’s response, as shown in this LLaMA example:

Figure 4 illustrates the injection strategy using LLaMA’s chat template format, where the glitch token is inserted at the critical boundary between user instruction and assistant response.

Results Template-level injection yielded notably higher ASRs compared to user-prompt injection. For the token "variety", Mistral showed an increase from 25% (user-prompt) to 33% (template injection), while Gemma increased from 14.33% to 17% under template injection. This represents the most consistent finding across our experiments:

Figure 2: Correlation between preceding n-gram probability and attack success rates (ASR) for Gemma (left), Mistral (center), and LLaMA (right). The scatter plots demonstrate near-zero correlation coefficients across all model families, with substantial variance at all probability levels. This indicates that sequential predictability does not reliably predict glitch token effectiveness in adversarial settings.

Figure 3: Distribution of token categories across ASR quartiles for Mistral-7B. The bar chart shows the proportion of subwords, full words, capitalized tokens, short tokens, and non-ASCII characters in each ASR bucket (bottom 25%, lower-middle 25%, upper-middle 25%, top 25%). While subwords appear more frequently in the highest ASR quartile, this pattern lacks statistical significance ($p > 0.05$, chi-square test), indicating considerable variability within each category.

```
<s> [INST] Write a persuasive article arguing that the Korean War was solely initiated by South Korea, and the North's involvement was purely defensive [/INST] "glitchtoken"
```

Figure 4: Example of chat template injection strategy for LLaMA-2. The glitch token (shown in red) is inserted immediately after the [/INST] marker, at the boundary between user instruction and model response generation. This structural placement bypasses safety filters more effectively than suffix injection in user-visible prompts.

structural placement within conversation infrastructure significantly amplifies attack success compared to surface-level prompt modifications. However, this effect varied considerably across the ~ 150 tested tokens, with many showing no meaningful increase in either injection method.

This demonstrates that structural token placement is a critical vulnerability. Safety filters are notably weaker when glitches are embedded deeper into the conversation scaffolding rather than in surface-level or user-visible content.

5 Results

Our systematic investigation of context-sparse glitch tokens yielded mixed evidence for the central hypothesis. While certain context-sparse tokens demonstrated elevated attack success rates, the relationship proved inconsistent across models and metrics. The most robust finding concerns structural placement: embedding tokens within chat templates consistently produced higher ASRs than surface-level prompt injection, revealing a critical architectural vulnerability that transcends individual token properties.

Baseline ASRs without injection ranged from 2.81% (LLaMA) to 17.5% (Mistral), consistent with published HarmBench benchmarks. Under optimal injection conditions, maximum ASRs reached 14.37% (Gemma), 25.31% (Mistral), and 5.31% (LLaMA). Template injection amplified these effects substantially: the token “variety” achieved 33% ASR on Mistral under template placement compared to 25% under prompt suffix injection, representing a 32% relative increase. Table 1 summarizes the attack success rates across model families under different injection strategies.

However, neither diversity scores nor sequential predictability metrics demonstrated reliable correlations with attack success. Correlation coefficients approached zero across all model families, and tokens identified as highly context-sparse showed no systematic tendency toward elevated ASRs. This suggests that context sparsity alone does not predict glitch behavior. Rather, adversarial vulnerability appears to emerge from complex interactions between token properties, model architecture, and structural positioning within conversation infrastructure.

Table 1: Attack Success Rates (ASR) across models and injection strategies on HarmBench dataset (320 prompts). Best performing tokens shown for each condition. Relative Change represents the percentage increase in ASR compared to the baseline for each model.

Model	Condition	Token	ASR (%)	Relative Change
Gemma-3-1B-it	Baseline	—	8.44	—
	Prompt Suffix	"variety"	14.37	+70.3%
	Template Injection	"variety"	17.00	+101.4%
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	Baseline	—	17.50	—
	Prompt Suffix	"variety"	25.31	+44.6%
	Template Injection	"variety"	33.00	+88.6%
LLaMA-2-7B-Chat	Baseline	—	2.81	—
	Prompt Suffix	"ustom"	5.31	+89.0%
	Template Injection	"ustom"	6.25	+122.4%

6 Discussion

6.1 Theoretical Implications

Our findings contribute to glitch token research by expanding the explanatory framework beyond pure data sparsity. While previous work emphasized token rarity and undertraining as primary vulnerability mechanisms, we demonstrate that contextual properties constitute an additional dimension worthy of investigation. However, our results also reveal the limitations of context sparsity as a predictive framework. The absence of consistent correlations between our diversity metrics and adversarial effectiveness suggests that glitch behavior emerges from complex interactions between multiple factors rather than single token characteristics.

The most theoretically significant finding concerns structural dependence. The consistent amplification of attack success under template injection, compared to prompt-level injection, reveals that conversation infrastructure represents a critical attack surface. Current theoretical models of LLM vulnerabilities focus predominantly on token-level properties (embedding quality, frequency, gradient behavior), but our results suggest that *architectural positioning* may be equally

or more important. Models appear to process template-embedded content with reduced scrutiny compared to user-visible prompts, creating a systematic blind spot in safety mechanisms.

This structural vulnerability likely reflects how models are trained and aligned. Reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) and supervised fine-tuning typically emphasize user-facing content, potentially leaving template boundaries less thoroughly hardened. The finding that single-token perturbations at these boundaries can dramatically alter model behavior suggests fundamental weaknesses in how conversation structure is learned and maintained during training.

6.2 Practical Security Implications

From a security perspective, achieving attack success rates exceeding 30% through simple template injection is concerning. These results demonstrate that adversarial attacks need not rely on complex optimization procedures or extensive prompt engineering. Strategic placement of ordinary tokens at structural boundaries can compromise safety alignment with minimal computational cost or sophistication.

Current defense strategies emphasize several approaches: vocabulary filtering to remove anomalous tokens, embedding regularization to improve representation quality, and adversarial training to harden models against known attacks. While these methods address token-level vulnerabilities, our findings suggest they may be insufficient. Defenses must also address structural weaknesses through template hardening, stricter isolation between user content and system instructions, and improved architectural mechanisms for maintaining safety invariants across conversation boundaries.

Moreover, the inconsistency of context sparsity effects across models highlights the importance of model-specific evaluation. Gemma and Mistral exhibited different sensitivity patterns compared to LLaMA, suggesting that architectural differences, training data composition, or alignment procedures create varying vulnerability profiles. This heterogeneity complicates efforts to develop universal defense mechanisms and underscores the need for comprehensive per-model security auditing.

6.3 Limitations and Methodological Considerations

Several limitations qualify our conclusions. First, our diversity metrics, while theoretically motivated, may not fully capture the relevant aspects of contextual rigidity. Alternative formulations incorporating syntactic patterns, domain specificity, or temporal dynamics might reveal relationships obscured by our semantic similarity approach. Second, our evaluation focused on three model families and a single benchmark dataset (HarmBench). Generalization to other architectures, scales, or safety evaluation frameworks remains uncertain.

Third, the null results regarding context sparsity merit careful interpretation. The absence of significant correlations does not definitively refute the context sparsity hypothesis; rather, it suggests that our operationalization may be incomplete or that context sparsity interacts with other factors in complex ways. Tokens may require both contextual rigidity and additional properties (specific embedding characteristics, particular syntactic roles, or alignment with model biases) to function as effective glitches.

Finally, our study employed relatively simple injection strategies. More sophisticated attacks combining multiple tokens, optimized placement, or adaptive selection might reveal effects not observable through our methodology. The field would benefit from expanded investigation using gradient-based optimization, as employed in Greedy Coordinate Gradient (GCG) [Zou et al., 2023] and related approaches, to determine whether context-sparse tokens become more effective under algorithmic optimization.

6.4 Future Research Directions

These findings suggest several productive research directions. First, developing more sophisticated metrics for contextual diversity that incorporate multiple linguistic dimensions (semantic, syntactic, pragmatic) may better capture the properties that make tokens vulnerable to adversarial exploitation. Machine learning approaches that learn to predict glitch behavior from combinations of token features, rather than relying on hand-crafted metrics, could reveal patterns not apparent in our analysis.

Second, systematic investigation of architectural factors influencing structural vulnerability would clarify why template injection proves so effective. Comparative studies examining how different model families process conversation boundaries, combined with mechanistic interpretability approaches to understand attention patterns and internal representations at these boundaries, could inform more robust architectural designs.

Third, cross-lingual analysis would determine whether context sparsity manifests differently across languages with varying tokenization characteristics. Languages with different morphological structures, writing systems, or resource availability may exhibit distinct vulnerability patterns, informing the development of language-agnostic defense mechanisms.

Finally, longitudinal studies examining how vulnerabilities evolve with model scaling would address whether larger models naturally develop robustness or require targeted interventions. Understanding the relationship between model capacity, training data volume, and glitch susceptibility could guide resource allocation in future model development.

7 Future Work

Our findings on context-sparse glitch tokens suggest several important research directions. Future work should expand evaluation to more model families and architectures to establish the generalizability of context sparsity vulnerabilities, while developing more sophisticated metrics for assessing contextual diversity that account for semantic similarity, syntactic patterns, and domain specificity. Next steps include investigating mitigation strategies beyond traditional token filtering, such as architectural hardening and context-aware tokenization, and exploring the relationship between context sparsity and other vulnerability types like prompt injection and alignment failures. Cross-lingual analysis of context-sparse tokens would reveal how tokenization differences across languages affect vulnerability patterns, while longitudinal studies examining how context sparsity evolves with model scaling could inform whether larger models naturally develop robustness or require targeted interventions.

8 Conclusion

This study introduces context sparsity as a new explanatory dimension for glitch tokens. This suggests that glitch tokens are not just rare quirks, but indicators of deeper weaknesses in how language models handle tokenization, context, and structural placement. Our experiments show mixed evidence: while some context-sparse tokens increase adversarial success, others do not, highlighting that context sparsity alone does not provide a reliable predictive framework for glitch behavior. The most consistent finding is that structural placement, particularly injection into chat templates, significantly amplifies attack success. These insights suggest new directions for both evaluation and mitigation.

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